

Effect of Compensation, Spirit at work and Communication On Employee Performance

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received Feb 21, 2024 Revised March 16, 2024 Accepted Apr 17, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Compensation, Spirit at Work, Communication, Employee Performance..</p>	<p>This research aims to determine the effect of compensation, work morale, communication on employee performance at REM. Company with a quantitative research method using SPSS statistical data, data was taken based on a questionnaire with likert scale calculations given to 48 REM Company employees and the research results can be processed to show that the Compensation variable has a significant effect on Employee Performance. Spirit at Work has a significant effect on Employee Performance. Communication has a significant effect on employee performance. Communication has a significant effect on employee performance.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p> <div style="text-align: right;"> </div>

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INTRODUCTION

Economic competition in the business world which is growing rapidly in the current era of globalization has triggered increasingly tighter business competition between companies. Consumers demand quality products at low prices for products produced by companies, and time is an important element in competition in the business environment. Companies, both private and government, must display innovation in the field of human resources, therefore human resources are assets that must be maintained and improved effectively and efficiently so that optimal performance will be achieved. One component of human resources that is very important for an organization or the company is an employee who can be reflected through performance. Therefore, organizations need to respect all aspects of employees in order to create quality human resources and superior performance (Arianto, 2017).

To improve employee performance, communication factors must be needed so that they can interact with each other so that good teamwork can be formed, therefore there is a need for good communication between the elements within the company. Communication creates mutual understanding in teamwork, communication plays an important role but is often ignored by some companies so that misunderstanding (misperception) often occurs. Communication can flow vertically or horizontally, where the vertical dimension is downward and upward communication. Vertical communication flows from one level in a group or organization to a lower level, this pattern is where a leader or manager uses it for work, informing, giving work instructions to subordinates, while upward communication flows to a higher level and this communication is used to provide feedback. to superiors in informing about progress on targets and conveying problems faced. The next step in maximizing the capabilities and potential of human resources in the organization is by providing places for employees in positions according to their abilities by dividing work according to their respective work units and in the division of work the work is divided into work portions in the organization or company with efforts makes it easier for someone to carry out tasks and work that allows them to learn and have adequate work skills and is able to work and is experienced in their work to be responsible for the tasks given by their superiors.

Good employee performance from a company's employees will lead to good productivity in a company, errors at work can be minimized, and cooperation between company employees can be maintained. This research uses compensation, work morale, and communication in improving the performance of company employees, especially at REM Company

Based on the background above, the objectives of this research are as follows. To determine the significant influence of compensation, Spirit at Work and communication simultaneously on employee performance at REM Company

Employee performance

Basically, performance is defined as something to be achieved, the achievements demonstrated and a person's abilities. There are many opinions that want to be given about performance, although the formulas are different, but from the many definitions, the broad meaning of performance is still the process of achieving results.

According to Nurusyifa (2018) "performance is about doing work and the results achieved from that work". So in essence, several definitions of employee performance from several experts have almost the same emphasis, namely the comparison of the work results achieved by employees with the standards determined by a company. Performance also means the results achieved by a person, both quantity and quality, in an organization in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Factors Affecting Performance

According to Putrana (2016) the factors that influence employee performance are:

1. Ability and Expertise Factors

It is the ability or skill that a person has in doing a job. The more abilities and expertise you have, the more you will be able to complete the job.

2. Work environment

It is the atmosphere or conditions around the work location. The work environment can include space, layout, facilities and infrastructure as well as working relationships with colleagues.

3. Organizational culture

These are habits or norms that apply and are owned by an organization.

Spirit at work

Every company wants every employee or employee to have high work enthusiasm. This work spirit is needed so that the company's operational activities in achieving its goals can run smoothly. Work enthusiasm is a characteristic that every employee must have so that the work done is not only completed quickly but the quality is also good. Achieving employee expectations will increase employee morale.

According to Nurusyifa (2018) work spirit is the willingness of a group of people to work together diligently and consistently in pursuing a common goal. Work enthusiasm makes the tasks carried out by the leadership quickly and easily completed and the results are maximized because employees are enthusiastic and enthusiastic in carrying out the work. Spirit at Works is often related to employees' attitudes or behavior towards the work they do. By paying attention and observing employees' attitudes and behavior towards their work, it can be seen to what extent the employee has worked productively, where high productivity can be achieved by employees who have high work enthusiasm. tall. According to Nitisemito in Agustina, et al (2019), work enthusiasm is doing work more actively so that work can be expected to be faster and better. It can be concluded that Spirit at Work is a description of the feelings, desires or sincerity of individuals/groups towards the organization which will influence the discipline and willingness of individuals in organizational activities to carry out tasks better and faster.

Compensation

Compensation is everything that employees receive as remuneration for their work (Agustina, et al, 2018), compensation is all income in the form of money, direct or indirect goods that employees receive as compensation for services provided by the company (Agustina, et al, 2019). The aim of providing compensation is a bond of cooperation, job satisfaction, effective procurement, motivation, employee stability, work discipline, as well as the influence of labor unions and the government.

The compensation provided by the company to its employees certainly has a positive impact which can provide benefits for both the company and the employees. The following are the positive impacts that the company or organization gets as follows:

1. Encourage employees to always excel and work diligently.
2. Can also be an attraction for quality job seekers.

3. The company's image looks better than competitors.
4. Companies can get quality work.
5. Simplify the administrative process and existing legal aspects.

Communication

There are several perceptions regarding the meaning of perceptual communication. According to Arianto (2017), communication is the sending and receiving of complex information. Included in this field are internal communication, human relations, managerial union relations, downward communication or communication from above to subordinates. Upward communication or communication from subordinates to their superiors, horizontal communication or communication from people at the same level or level in the organization, communication skills, and speaking, writing and program evaluation.

According to Fachrezi, et al (2020) that communication is the flow of information, the exchange of thoughts or information, and the transfer of meaning within a company. Based on this definition, it can be concluded that communication is the flow of information, exchange of information and transfer of meaning within an organization which is complex and can be divided into two types, namely: internal communication and external communication aimed at achieving something.

Hypothesis

H1: Compensation has a significant effect on employee performance at REM Company

H2: Spirit at Work has a significant effect on employee performance at REM Company

H3: Communication has a significant effect on employee performance at REM Company

Framework

Based on the description above, a research paradigm can be formulated regarding Compensation, Spirit of Work and Communication influencing Employee Performance, expressed in the following paradigm.

METHODS

Population and Sampling Techniques

Population

Population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population is the object and all the characteristics or traits possessed by the

subject or object under study (Sugiyono, 2019:126). Based on this research, the population taken in this research at REM Company is 48 employees.

Sample

Sampling was carried out using a probability sampling technique with non-probability sampling (saturated sampling). Non-probability sampling is a sampling technique that provides equal opportunities for each element (member) of the sample to be selected as a member of the sample, namely 48 employees (Sugiyono 2019:127).

Research Instrument

In quantitative research, the data analysis techniques used are clear, namely directed at answering problem formulations or testing hypotheses that have been formulated. Because the data is quantitative, the data analysis techniques use statistical methods that are already available. Quantitative data analysis uses data in the form of numbers obtained as a result of measurements or additions from questionnaires. To obtain quantitative data, a Likert scale was used which was obtained from a list of questions classified into five levels Sugiyono (2019; 90), in this study the researcher used five levels of the Likert scale. The following is an example of a Likert scale that will be used in research:

- 1) For answers that strongly disagree, a score of =1
- 2) For answers that do not agree, a score of = 2
- 3) For answers that are quite agree, a score of = 3
- 4) For an affirmative answer, a score of = 4
- 5) The answer strongly agree a score of =5

The analytical tool used to test the hypothesis that has been put forward regarding the influence of standard operational procedures, training and organizational commitment on employee performance is by using data validity and data reliability tests, with the help of the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Description of Research Objects

The research subjects used in this research were employees who worked at REM company. The objects used in this research are compensation, work morale, communication and employees performance of REM Company

REM company that operates in the field of environmental processing for residents of the Royal Residence housing complex. This institution is an environmental monitoring element led by a director, who is in charge. In his duties are to be directly responsible to the residents of the royal residence housing complex.

Research result

Data collection was carried out by distributing research questionnaires directly to employees who work at REM Company. The number of questionnaires distributed was 48 sheets. There were 48 questionnaires returned and completely filled out, according to the number of REM Company employees. The percentage of questionnaire data collection is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B		
Konstanta	-0,213	-0,292	-0,772
Compensation (X ₁)	0,366	2,414	0,020
Spirit of Work (X ₂)	0,263	2,127	0,039
Communication(X ₃)	0,332	2,490	0,017

Hypothesis Test-Partial Test (T)

Table 2. Partial Test Results (T)

t Test Result			t Test Result			Sig.
Model	t	Sig.	Model	t		Sig.
Constant	-0,292	0,772	Constant	-0,292		.000
Compensation (X ₁)	2,414	0,020	Compensation (X ₁)	2,414		.003

Source: Primary Data (processed), 2024

Based on the above tests, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Effect of Compensation on Employee Performance

Based on the calculation results in table 2, the regression coefficient value is positive and the significance value for Compensation is $\alpha = 0.020 < 0.05$, indicating that Compensation has a significant influence on Employee Performance. H1 which states the alleged influence of compensation on employee performance is accepted.

2. The Effect of Spirit at Work on Employee Performance

The results of the calculations in table 2 show that the regression coefficient value is positive and the significance value for Spirit at Work is $\alpha = 0.039 < 0.05$, indicating that Work Spirit has a significant influence on Employee Performance. H2 which states the alleged influence of Spirit at Work on Employee Performance is accepted.

3. The Effect of Communication on Employee Performance

The results of table 2 calculations show that the regression coefficient value is positive and the significance value for Communication is $\alpha = 0.017 < 0.05$, indicating that Communication has a significant influence on Employee Performance. H3 which states the alleged influence of Communication on Employee Performance is accepted.

Hypothesis Test-Coefficient Of Determination Test R²

This test was conducted to see how much the variables of fear of missing out, product quality, and halal awareness contribute to purchasing decisions. quality, and halal awareness contribute to purchasing decisions.

DISCUSSION

This research examines the influence of compensation, the effect of spirit at Works on employee performance and communication on employee performance.

1. The Effect of Compensation on Employee Performance

Compensation has a significant influence on employee performance, this is proven by a significant value of 0.020, which is smaller than 0.05. This means that the Compensation variable has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

Compensation is all income in the form of money, direct or indirect goods received by employees as compensation for services provided by the company (Aryaningtyas, 2019). The aim of providing compensation is a bond of cooperation, job satisfaction, effective procurement, motivation, employee stability, work discipline, as well as the influence of labor unions and the government.

These results are in accordance with research conducted by Utari (2018) which found that compensation has an effect on employee performance.

2. The Effect of Spirit at Works on Employee Performance

Spirit at Work has a significant influence on Employee Performance, this is proven by the significance value of 0.039 which is smaller than 0.05. This means that the Spirit at Work variable has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

According to Leighton (2018) Work Spirit is the willingness of a group of people to work together diligently and consistently in pursuing a common goal. Work enthusiasm makes the tasks carried out by the leadership quickly and easily completed and the results are maximized because employees are enthusiastic and enthusiastic in carrying out the work. This result is inversely proportional to research conducted by Tika (2019) stating that Spirit at Work has no effect on Employee Performance.

3. The Effect of Communication on Employee Performance

Communication has a significant influence on employee performance, this is proven by a significant value of 0.017, which is smaller than 0.05. this means that the Communication variable has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

According to Samborn (2015), communication is the sending and receiving of complex information. Included in this field are internal communication, human relations, managerial union relations, downward communication or communication from above to subordinates. Upward communication or communication from subordinates to their superiors, horizontal communication or communication from people at the same level or level in the organization, communication skills, and speaking, writing and program evaluation.

These results are in accordance with research conducted by Arianto (2015), proving that communication influences employee performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis that has been carried out, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. That the Compensation variable has a significant influence on Employee Performance.
2. That the Work Morale variable has a significant influence on Employee Performance.
3. That the Communication variable has a significant influence on Employee Performance.

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